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Research Article

STUDY TO REVEAL THE FREQUENCY OF HBsAg, ANTI-HCV, VDRL AND HIV POSITIVE CASES AMONG BLOOD DONORS

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Abstract:

Objective: To investigate the frequency of positive HIV, anti-HCV, HBsAg and VDRL cases among apparently healthy blood donors.

Study Design: A Prospective Study.

Place and Duration of study: In the Department of Medicine and Blood bank section of Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur for Six month Duration from March 2018 to August 2018.

Methods: All blood donors were selected for this study. For detection of diseases a rapid diagnostic test kit named "Accu Check" was used. 50 infected donors were found from 833 blood donors. No donors were HIV-positive, but 24 were positive for VDRL, 16 were positive for HCV, and 10 were positive for HBsAg. The individual patient did not suffer more than the infectious disease mentioned above. Not any patient did not suffer more than the infectious disease mentioned above.

Results: Of the 833 blood donors, 50 (6%) were donors. No donors were HIV positive, but VDRL positive in 24 (2.88%) donors, anti-HCV positive in 17 (1.71%) and HBsAg positive in 10 (1.19%). Not any patient did not suffer more than the infectious disease mentioned above. In addition, a total of 50 infected donors, 24 (48%) were positive for VDRL, 16 (32%) were positive for HCV and 10 (20%) were positive for HBV. In addition, 8 of the infected people worked together with A +, B + in 16 work together, 10 with O +, 12 with AB +, 2 with B-, 2 with A- and none with O- or AB. .

Conclusion: It was concluded that appropriate examination was mandatory to stop blood-borne infectious diseases.

Keywords: HIV, DCRL, HBsAg.

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INTRODUCTION:

Infectious diseases are the main cause of mortality and morbidity in the world. Carriers are a moving and alarming threat to a healthy population. The most important forms of transmission of infectious diseases is blood circulation. Preventive measures, such as the appropriate choice of donor transfusions, are of vital importance. Detection of HBV, HCV, HIV and VDRL is a prerequisite prior to transfusion of blood. For chronic liver disease worldwide the most common causes are Hepatitis C (HCV) and Hepatitis B viruses (HBV). Both viruses results in chronic hepatitis, which may leads to cirrhosis and ultimately hepatocellular carcinoma. Although the HCV and HBV virus prevalence in the world is 480 million, the combined infection rate in Pakistan is 7.06% in the general population. (HIV) Human immunodeficiency virus is a lentivirus (slow retrovirus replication) that results in (AIDS) acquired immunodeficiency syndrome. HIV in Pakistan is not epidemic dominantly currently. However, the number of patients are increasing. The most recent figures from the National AIDS Program show that since 1986 more than 3950 HIV cases have been reported,

but the government and UN suggests have raised the number of AIDS/ HIV cases to 96,500 with the lowest estimate. The highest estimate from 46,000 (210,000). A venereal disease is a blood test for laboratory testing of VDRL or syphilis. Syphilis is a sexually transmitted disease caused by bacteria spirochete *treponema pallidum*. With regard to syphilis, there is no real prevalence estimate in Pakistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This Prospective Study was held in the Department of Medicine and Blood bank section of Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur for Six month Duration from March 2018 to August 2018. Selection was made with the quick diagnostic test kit "Accu Check". A total of 833 donors were examined. All male donors weighing > 60 kg between the ages of 21-36 with hemoglobin > 14 g / dl were selected for the analysis. In this study, donors with a history of HCV, HBV, HIV or VDRL who were drug abusers or having tuberculosis, body piercing, surgery, transfusion of blood or blood components within 3 months were not selected for analysis.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS:

Blood-borne infectious diseases can remain asymptomatic for decades because they are silent throughout the disease period. To healthy populations, Such carriers are sign that care should be taken. Uncontrolled transfusion of silent carriers to receptors is the main cause of blood-borne infections. The results showed that 50 (6%) donors were infected with 833 blood donors. No donors were

HIV-positive, 25 (2.90%) were positive VDRL donors, 17 (1.89%) were HCV and 11 (1.19) were positive for HBsAg. The individual patient did not suffer any more than the above-mentioned infectious disease. In addition, 24 (48%) of 50 infected donors were positive for a total VDRL, 16 (32%), HCV and 10 (20%) were positive for HBV. In addition, 8 of the infected individuals had an O- or AB-O + 2 A, B- and 2 A + B + 16, + 12 AB 10.

CONCLUSION

Uncontrolled blood transfusion plays an important role in the spread of infectious diseases. This risk can be minimized only by a trained staff and a suitable detection method used by a quality tool. During the assessment, all findings should be recorded in the OPD for further treatment and advice. This shows that the iceberg's phenomenon in our population must be taken and the need to take preventive and corrective measures in this regard. "In order to raise awareness of this hot topic, the material of IEC (information-training-communication) should be widely distributed among the local population.

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